

REACTIVITY OF $\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ -GROUP ATTACHED TO AN AROMATIC NUCLEUS.

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α -Chloro derivatives of the condensation products of chloral with hydroxy- and methoxybenzoic acids have been prepared by an improved method and the reactivity of the α -chlorine atom towards potassium iodide, potassium cyanide, ammonia and aniline have been investigated and it is found that the methoxy group in the nucleus has an inhibiting influence on the α -chlorine atom.

Compounds containing the group $\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ have been obtained by a number of investigators in the course of their study of the condensation products of chloral with phenols and hydroxybenzoic acids (Chattaway and Calvet, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2914; Shah and Alimchandani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 253; 1931, 8, 261; Hurry and Meldrum, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 535). As very little work has been done so far regarding the behaviour of the $\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ group, an attempt has been made by the present authors to study the reactivity of this group in general and of the α -chlorine atom in particular.

The tetrachloro compound, $\text{R}\cdot\text{CHCl}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$, is usually derived from the chloral condensation product containing $\text{CHOH}\cdot\text{CCl}_3$ group by (a) saturating the sulphuric acid solution of the substance with dry hydrochloric acid gas (*cf.* Chattaway and Calvet, *loc. cit.*), (b) treatment with hot concentrated sulphuric acid (*cf.* Shah and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*), and (c) the interaction of thionyl chloride or phosphorus pentachloride (*cf.* Feist, Nissen and Städler, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1173; Hurry and Meldrum, *loc. cit.*). In the present investigation, however, it has been found that the yield and purity of the product can be considerably increased by producing hydrochloric acid gas *in situ* by adding sodium chloride to the sulphuric acid solution of the substance.

Employing the above method, 2-hydroxy-5- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzoic acid (I) and 4-hydroxy-5- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzoic acid (II) have been prepared from salicylic and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids respectively in addition to the corresponding methoxy compounds (III) and (IV) already obtained from methoxysalicylic acid (Hurry and Meldrum, *loc. cit.*; Shah and Alimchandani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 476), and from anisic acid (Chattaway and Calvet, *loc. cit.*) respectively. But attempts to obtain

similar compounds from *m*-hydroxy- and *m*-methoxybenzoic acids failed owing to the formation of the phthalide ring (Fritsch, *Annalen*, 1897, 276, 344).

Each of the above tetrachloro compounds, $\text{R-CHCl}_2\text{-CCl}_2$, can be reduced to R-CH:CCl_2 by means of zinc dust and acetic acid. These will be described in a subsequent paper.

A solution of potassium iodide in acetone or alcohol easily removes the α - and β -chlorine atom from the hydroxy compounds yielding ethylene derivatives identical with the above-mentioned reduction products (*cf.* Van Duin, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1926, 45, 345; Dillong and co-workers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1953); thus (I) and (II) give 2-hydroxy-, and 4-hydroxy-5- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic acids respectively. The methoxy compounds (III) and (IV), however, are unaffected. The compound (I) on interaction with ammonia and aniline gives 2-hydroxy-5-*o*-amino- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzoic acid and 2-hydroxy-5-*o*-amino- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzoic acid respectively. The action of potassium cyanide is interesting. The replacement of α -chlorine atom by the CN group is accompanied by the elimination of a molecule of HCl as well during the reaction thus giving 2-hydroxy-5-*o*-cyano- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic acid (V), R-C(CN):CCl_2 .

The hydrolysis of CN group to COOH by means of concentrated hydrochloric or sulphuric acid could not be accomplished. Alkali, however, easily hydrolyses the side-chain giving 4-hydroxy-5-carboxyphenylacetic acid.

It is significant that the hydroxy compounds (I) and (II) are very unstable even towards cold dilute alkali, but no definite product could be isolated. The methoxy compounds (III) and (IV), on the other hand, are sufficiently stable to cold dilute alkali. Treatment with hot aqueous alkali, however, eliminates a molecule of hydrochloric acid furnishing 4-, and 2-methoxy-5-carboxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -trichlorostyrene respectively (*cf.* Shah and Alimchandani, *loc. cit.*)

Similarly it is interesting to note that (III) and (IV) do not react with potassium cyanide, potassium iodide, ammonia and aniline [contrast the behaviour of the corresponding hydroxy compounds (I) and (II).]

The authors believe that the inactivity of the α -chlorine atom of the methoxy derivatives is due to the OMe group which causes a large diminution in the ionising tendency of the α -chlorine by a supply of electrons and as a result the halogen atom becomes resistant towards anionic attack like ammonia, aniline, potassium iodide and potassium cyanide (*cf.* Baddeley and Bennet, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 265).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-Hydroxy-5- α $\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzoic Acid (I).—Chloral hydrate (40 g.) and salicylic acid (28 g.) were dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (200 c.c.) in a pressure bottle and sodium chloride (12 g.) was quickly added, and the bottle was kept sealed with paraffin for 2 days. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice when a pasty mass separated which solidified on washing with water. It was first crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then from carbon tetrachloride in shining rhombic plates, m.p. 182-83°, yield 25 g. The compound decomposes in presence of alkali and gives violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: Cl, 46.71. $C_9H_6O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 46.69 per cent).

The compound was also obtained by dissolving 2-hydroxy-5- α hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzoic acid (5 g. Calvet and Mejuto, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 554) in concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) and saturating the solution with dry hydrochloric acid gas.

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from chloroform in thin plates, m.p. 146-47°. (Found: Cl, 41.44. $C_{11}H_8O_4Cl_4$ requires Cl, 41.0 per cent).

The *anilide* was crystallised from chloroform in yellowish silky needles, m.p. 201-2°. (Found: Cl, 37.36. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2NCl_4$ requires Cl, 37.41 per cent).

The *p-toluidide* crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum benzene in thin leaflets, m.p. 178-79°. (Found: Cl, 36.12; $C_{13}H_{13}O_2NCl_4$ requires Cl, 36.07 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5- α -amino- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzoic Acid.—The tetrachloro compound (I, 5g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit (50 c.c.) and liquor ammonia (d 0.9) was added till there was a distinct smell of ammonia and shaken well for 2 hours. After 5 days the excess of ammonia was removed under reduced pressure in a vacuum desiccator. The solution was diluted with about 20 c.c. of water, evaporated on a water-bath to a small bulk and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a tarry oil separated. After the removal of the tar the solution slowly deposited a crystalline product which crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 212° with previous charring at 183-84°. It dissolves in sodium hydroxide with purple colouration and gives out ammonia and carbylamine on heating the solution. (Found: Cl, 37.93; N, 4.9. $C_9H_6O_3NCl_3$ requires Cl, 37.5; N, 4.92 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5- α -anilino- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethylbenzoic Acid.—A solution of (I, 3 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.) and aniline (1.3 g.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. The solid product obtained on cooling was crystallised

from benzene. It was recrystallised from rectified spirit in lustrous rhombic plates, m.p. 182° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 29.81. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$, requires Cl, 29.50 per cent).

Reduction of (I) by Zinc dust and Acetic Acid: 2-Hydroxy-5- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic Acid.—Zinc dust (2 g.) was added gradually to a hot solution of (I, 5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.). After the reaction was over the solution was quickly filtered and diluted with water when a mass of soft silky needles separated. It was filtered off and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 170° .

It does not absorb bromine in either acetic acid or chloroform solution. It decolourises permanganate and gives blue ferric reaction. (Found: C, 46.53; H, 2.73; Cl, 30.10. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$ requires C, 46.35; H, 2.6; Cl, 30.44 per cent).

Action of Potassium Iodide on (I). 2-Hydroxy-5- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic Acid.—Potassium iodide (3.5 g.) was added to a solution of (I, 3 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) and refluxed on a water-bath for about 15 minutes. After removing iodine by steam distillation, needle-shaped crystals were deposited which crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. $170-71^\circ$.

2-Hydroxy-5- α -cyano- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic Acid (V).—An aqueous solution of potassium cyanide (2 g.) was added to the solution of (I, 5 g.) in rectified spirit (30 c.c.) and refluxed for 2 hours on a water-bath. The solution was filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a pasty mass was obtained which was washed with water, dried on a porous plate and crystallised from a mixture of acetone and benzene in fine silky needles, m.p. $224-25^\circ$. It gives with ferric chloride a violet colouration. (Found: Cl, 27.66; N, 5.45. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2$ requires Cl, 27.49; N, 5.43 per cent).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from rectified spirit in double pyramids, m.p. $175-76^\circ$. (Found: Cl, 23.72. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{O}_4\text{NCl}_2$ requires Cl, 23.63 per cent).

The dibromide was obtained by adding bromine to the substance dissolved in acetic acid. The product crystallised from benzene in white silky needles, m.p. 210° . (Found: Halogen, 55.72. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{NCl}_2\text{Br}_2$ requires Halogen, 55.26 per cent).

Hydrolysis of (V) by Alcoholic Potash: 4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenylacetic Acid.—The compound (V, 5 g.) was refluxed with 20% alcoholic potash (25 c.c.) for 3 hours until the evolution of ammonia ceased. The solution was acidified and extracted with ether. On removing ether, a gelatinous mass was obtained which was first crystallised from acetic acid and then from chloroform in rhombic plates, m.p. 207° . (Found: C, 54.97;

H, 4'23; Equiv., 97'24. $C_9H_8O_3$ requires C, 55'09; H, 4'11 per cent. Equiv., 98'08).

Oxidation of (V): Formation of 4-Hydroxyisophthalic Acid.—The compound (V, 1 g.) was dissolved in 5% sodium hydroxide solution making the solution just faintly alkaline. Hydrogen peroxide (12 vol., 15 c.c.) was added, and the solution shaken well for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The product crystallised from a mixture of methyl alcohol and chloroform in needles, m.p. 303° (mixed m.p. with 4-hydroxyisophthalic acid).

4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzene.—Chloral hydrate (10 g.) and methoxysalicylic acid (8 g.) were dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (80 c.c.) and treated with sodium chloride (4 g.) as mentioned before. After 5 days, the mixture was poured into ice when a pasty mass separated, which solidified on washing with water. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then from rectified spirit in prismatic plates, m. p. 138°. (*cf.* Hurry and Meldrum, *loc. cit.* Shah and Alimchandani, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 475).

The *methyl ester* crystallised from benzene in long hexagonal plates, m.p. 105°. (Found: Cl, 42'65. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 42'71 per cent).

4-Methoxy-5-carboxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -trichlorovinylbenzene.—The above-mentioned compound (8 g.) was refluxed with 15% alcoholic potash (40 c.c.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was filtered, acidified and the product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in white silky needles, m.p. 151-52°, yield 3 g.

It does not absorb bromine in acetic acid, chloroform or carbon tetrachloride. Potassium permanganate is not decolourised in the cold. (Found: Cl, 37.69; Equiv., 281'1. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 37'82 per cent. Equiv., 281.4).

The *calcium salt* crystallises with $5\frac{1}{2}$ molecules of water of which $3\frac{1}{2}$ molecules are lost at 110°. [Found: Ca, 5'72. $(C_{10}H_6O_3Cl_3)_2Ca, 5\frac{1}{2} H_2O$ requires Ca, 5'73 per cent].

The *methyl ester* crystallises from benzene in long needles, m.p. 85°. (Found: Cl, 35'97. $C_{11}H_8O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 36'03 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-5- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzoic Acid (II).—*p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (20 g.) and chloral hydrate (30 g.) were dissolved in sulphuric acid (200 c.c.) and mixed with sodium chloride (6 g.) as usual. After a week the mixture was poured over ice and the pasty mass obtained was dried on a porous tile and crystallised first from glacial acetic acid and then from benzene-petroleum benzene in glistening rhombic plates, m.p. 142° (efferv.). Ferric chloride produces very feeble purple colouration. (Found: Cl, 46'65. $C_9H_6O_3Cl_4$ requires Cl, 46'69 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from rectified spirit in rectangular rods, m.p. $189\text{--}90^\circ$. (Found : Cl, $41\cdot32$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, $41\cdot0$ per cent).

Action of Potassium Iodide on (II) : 4-Hydroxy-5- $\beta\beta$ -dichlorovinylbenzoic Acid.—The compound (II, $1\cdot5$ g.) was dissolved in rectified spirit (10 c.c.) and refluxed with potassium iodide (9 g.) for 20 minutes. On dilution with water needle-shaped crystals were obtained which were recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 171° . (Found : Cl, $30\cdot23$. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$ requires Cl, $30\cdot44$ per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-carboxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta\beta$ -tetrachloroethylbenzene (cf. Chattaway and Calvet, *loc. cit.*).—Anisic acid (24 g.) and chloral hydrate (30 g.) were dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid and mixed with sodium chloride (12 g.) in the usual manner. After 3 days the mixture was poured over ice and the precipitated solid mass was first crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then from methyl alcohol in needles, m.p. $248\text{--}49^\circ$, yield 29 g.

The *methyl ester* crystallised from benzene in square plates, m.p. $110\text{--}11^\circ$. (Found : Cl, $42\cdot83$. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4$ requires Cl, $42\cdot71$ per cent).

2-Methoxy-5-carboxy-1- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -trichlorostyrene.—The above-mentioned compound (5 g.) was refluxed with 20% alcoholic potash (20 c.c.) for 15 minutes, the solution diluted with water and acidified. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in orange cubes, m.p. $212\text{--}13^\circ$. (Found : Cl, $37\cdot73$. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, $37\cdot82$ per cent).

